

CURRENT STATE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISE LOCATION IN UZBEKISTAN

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The Republic of Uzbekistan has implemented comprehensive reforms to fundamentally transform its economy since independence, including extensive initiatives for industrial development. In recent years, significant changes have occurred in the location and territorial distribution of industrial enterprises in the country. Favorable investment climate, tax incentives, infrastructure improvements, and the establishment of free economic zones provided by the state are stimulating more efficient location of industrial enterprises [1].

Industrial sector improvement, diversification, and modernization issues were identified as priority tasks in the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 and in the subsequent "New Uzbekistan" Development Strategy for 2022-2026 [2]. The industrial sector is one of the leading sectors in Uzbekistan's economy, and its development directly affects the country's economic stability and public welfare.

Table 1

Number of industrial enterprises by regions of Uzbekistan, as of January 1, 2024¹

Region	Number of enterprises	Share, %
Tashkent city	11,783	17.0
Fergana region	7,803	11.2
Tashkent region	7,284	10.5
Samarkand region	6,151	8.9
Andijan region	5,511	7.9
Namangan region	4,952	7.1
Kashkadarya region	3,776	5.4
Bukhara region	4,201	6.0
Khorezm region	4,039	5.8
Surkhandarya region	3,097	4.5
Navoi region	3,094	4.5
Jizzakh region	2,571	3.7
Syrdarya region	1,539	2.2
Republic of Karakalpakstan	3,666	5.3
Total	69,467	100.0

In recent years, the number of industrial enterprises operating in Uzbekistan has increased significantly. As of January 1, 2024, more than 69.4 thousand industrial enterprises are operating in the country. Industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan are distributed relatively unevenly. A large proportion of enterprises are concentrated in Tashkent city, Tashkent region, Fergana Valley, and Samarkand region.

Although Tashkent city leads in terms of number of industrial enterprises (17%), Fergana region (11.2%) and Tashkent region (10.5%) also have high indicators in terms of industrial production volume.

The territorial distribution of the number of industrial enterprises may not always correspond to the volume of industrial production. For example, in Navoi region, despite a relatively small number of enterprises, the volume of industrial production is high due to large metallurgical and chemical industry enterprises.

Table 2

Volume of industrial production by regions in 2024²

Region	Volume (trillion soums)	Share, %
Tashkent region	139.1	16.0
Tashkent city	170.8	19.7
Navoi region	145.1	16.7
Andijan region	90.6	10.4
Kashkadarya region	39.5	4.6
Fergana region	48.1	5.5
Samarkand region	46.2	5.3
Bukhara region	42.3	4.9
Namangan region	32.1	3.7
Khorezm region	29.1	3.4
Surkhandarya region	14.8	1.7
Republic of Karakalpakstan	24.6	2.8
Jizzakh region	25.8	3.0
Syrdarya region	19.9	2.3
Total	867.4	100.0

The following factors influence the location of industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan:

² [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://stat.uz/img/press-reлиз-yanvar-dekabr-2024/p85155_p70231_p70418.pdf](https://stat.uz/img/press-reлиз-yanvar-dekabr-2024/p85155_p70231_p70418.pdf)

1. **Proximity to raw material base:** Many industrial sectors in Uzbekistan are located close to raw material sources. For example, metallurgical enterprises are located near mining areas (Navoi, Almalyk, Bekabad), while light industry enterprises are located in cotton-growing regions (Fergana Valley, Bukhara, Khorezm) [3].

2. **Transport infrastructure:** Industrial enterprises are more commonly located in areas with well-developed railways and highways. Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, and Fergana Valley are considered transport-friendly regions.

3. **Labor resources:** Labor-intensive sectors (light industry, food industry) are more concentrated in large cities and densely populated areas.

4. **State policy and incentives:** Free economic zones, small industrial zones, and incentives provided under special programs have a significant impact on enterprise location.

5. **Energy resources:** Energy-intensive production enterprises (such as metallurgy, chemistry) are located in areas with sufficient electricity.

6. **Proximity to market:** Proximity to the consumer market is an important factor, especially for the food and construction materials industries.

The location of industrial enterprises has a significant impact on the state of the environment. Environmentally unfavorable enterprises should be located away from large population centers. However, in practice, this requirement is not always observed.

Table 3

Location of industrial sectors with the highest environmental impact³

Industrial sector	Location regions	Main environmental problems
Metallurgy	Navoi, Almalyk, Bekabad	Waste gases to the air, soil contamination with heavy metals
Oil and gas chemistry	Kashkadarya, Bukhara	Release of harmful substances into the atmosphere
Cement production	Navoi, Kashkadarya, Fergana	Dust, carbon dioxide gas
Electric power industry	Syrdarya, Navoi, Tashkent	Atmospheric pollution, changes in heat and water balance

In recent years, the government of Uzbekistan has adopted a number of regulatory documents on the placement of environmentally safe industrial

enterprises. Environmental expertise is mandatory for the construction of new enterprises.

The uneven distribution of industrial enterprises leads to regional economic inequality. The government of Uzbekistan is paying special attention to the construction and development of industrial enterprises in relatively less economically developed regions to address this problem.

Table 4

Volume of industrial production per capita in the regions of Uzbekistan (2024, million soums)⁴

Region	Industrial production per capita	Relative to the national average, %
Navoi region	133.7	472.4
Tashkent region	45.2	159.7
Tashkent city	55.5	196.1
Bukhara region	20.5	72.4
Kashkadarya region	11.0	38.9
Andijan region	26.4	74.3
Fergana region	11.7	93.3
Syrdarya region	21.6	76.3
Khorezm region	14.4	50.9
Republic of Karakalpakstan	12.2	43.1
Samarkand region	10.9	38.5
Jizzakh region	17.0	60.1
Surkhandarya region	5.1	18.0
Namangan region	10.3	36.4
National average	28.3	100.0

As can be seen from the table, the volume of industrial production per capita in Navoi region is 4.2 times higher than the national average, while in Namangan region this indicator is 2.4 times lower than the national average. This situation demonstrates regional inequality, and the government is implementing a number of programs to reduce this difference.

The current state of industrial enterprise location in Uzbekistan has been shaped, on the one hand, by natural resources and traditional factors, and on the other hand, is changing under the influence of state policy and modern economic trends.

⁴[chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://stat.uz/img/press-reliz-yanvar-dekabr-2024/p85155_p70231_p70418.pdf](https://stat.uz/img/press-reliz-yanvar-dekabr-2024/p85155_p70231_p70418.pdf)

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